

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New Xanthotoxin Derivatives

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Xanthotoxin-4-sulphonamides (2-12, 15-19), 4-sulphonates (13, 14), 4-sulphonyl-amino derivatives (21) and the pyrone ring opened products (22, 23) incorporating various substituents have been prepared. Antimicrobial activity tests showed some of the products to possess better efficacy than xanthotoxin.

XANTHOTOXIN, a furocoumarin constituent of *Ammi majus*¹, as well as some of its derivatives have been reported² to possess useful pharmacological activities. It was therefore of interest to prepare new derivatives incorporating other biologically active centres with a view to obtaining products exhibiting better activities.

The compounds 2-19 and 21-23 have been prepared from xanthotoxin itself or its 4-sulphonyl chloride (1) or 4-amino (20) derivative as described in the Experimental section. The structures have been established through elemental analyses, acidity

tests and ir spectrometry. In few cases, unequivocal chemical conversions have been used for confirmation.

Since sulphonamides exhibit remarkable bacteriostatic action³, the authors prepared some xanthotoxin derivatives which contain more than one sulphonamido group. Thus, interaction of xanthotoxin-4-sulphonyl chloride⁴ (1) with some sulpha derivatives furnished the required products (2a-e) whose structures were based on elemental analyses and ir spectra (ν_{NH} at 3 200 and ν_{SO_2} at 1 350, 1 160 cm^{-1}).

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The fact that *p*-aminobenzoic acid, its esters, mono- and di-alkylamides exhibit antituberculous⁵ and local anaesthetic⁶ activities led the authors to react **1** with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids to give **3a-c** whose structures were confirmed by elemental analyses, ir spectra (ν_{NH} and ν_{COOH} as broad band at 3 200–2 650 cm^{-1}) and positive test for acidity. Esterification of some of the above acids with alcohols furnished the corresponding esters (**4a-d**) (ir spectra showed the absence of ν_{COOH} and the presence of $\nu_{\text{CH}_{\text{Aliph}}}$ at 2 950 cm^{-1}). Interaction of **3c** with primary or secondary aliphatic amines in presence of PCl_5 gave the corresponding primary (**5a-d**) or secondary (**6a, b**) amides, respectively (ir spectra of **5** and **6** showed the disappearance of ν_{COOH}). The products **4-6** do not respond to the test for acidity.

Interaction of **1** with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminophenols gave **7a-c** (ν_{OH} and ν_{NH} at 3 400–3 200 cm^{-1}); gave a characteristic colouration with FeCl_3 . Alkylation of some of the products with different alkyl halides gave **8a-e** ($\nu_{\text{CH}_{\text{Aliph}}}$ at 2 950–2 900 cm^{-1}); the acylated derivatives **9a-d** (ν_{CO} as a broad band around 1 700 cm^{-1} due to the ester and δ -pyrone groups). Compounds **8** and **9** showed the disappearance of ν_{OH} while ν_{NH} was observed at 3 290 cm^{-1} and they did not give any colouration with FeCl_3 .

10

- 10a** ; R = H, R' = H
10b ; R = H, R' = COCH₃
10c ; R = H, R' = COCH₂Cl
10d ; R = COCH₃, R' = COCH₃

Interaction of **1** with *p*-aminodiphenylamine gave **10a** (ν_{NH} at 3 350 and $\nu_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}}$ at 3 150 cm^{-1}). Acylation of **10a** with either acetyl chloride or chloroacetyl chloride gave **10b,c** which showed the absence of ν_{NH} and the presence of $\nu_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}}$ at 3 150 cm^{-1} , while acetic anhydride furnished **10d** which showed the disappearance of both ν_{NH} and $\nu_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}}$. Repetition of acetylation of **10a** with acetyl chloride using anhydrous ZnCl_2 gave the acridine derivative (**11**) as demonstrated from its elemental analyses, ir spectra showing the disappearance of ν_{NH} and appearance of $\nu_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}}$ at 3 150 cm^{-1} , difference from **10b** in colour and m.p., and formation by fusion of **10b** with anhydrous ZnCl_2 at 170°.

11

12

Interaction of **10a** with sulphur flower in *o*-dichlorobenzene furnished the phenothiazine derivative (**12**; ν_{NH} at 3 300, $\nu_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}}$ at 3 150, ν_{COO} at 1 690 and $\nu_{\text{C-S-C}}$ at 750 cm^{-1}).

Direct interaction between **1** and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes gave the corresponding sulphonic esters (**13a-c**). The presence of the aldehyde group in **13** was established by interaction of **13c** with hippuric acid in Ac_2O containing AcONa as catalyst which gave the oxazoline-5-one derivative (**14**).

13

- 13a** ; R = C₆H₄CHO-*o*
13b ; R = C₆H₄CHO-*m*
13c ; R = C₆H₄CHO-*p*

14

Xanthotoxin-4-sulphonamide (**15a**) was prepared from **1** and ammonium hydroxide, while **15b-d** were prepared from **1** and the corresponding aliphatic amines ($\nu_{\text{SO}_2\text{NH}}$ at 3 200, $\nu_{\text{CH}_{\text{Aliph}}}$ at 2 950, ν_{COO} at 1 690 and $\nu_{\text{SO}_2\text{-N}}$ at 1 350 and 1 160 cm^{-1}).

17

- 17a** ; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = COCH₃
17b ; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = COCH₂Cl
17c ; R₁ = C₆H₅-*n*, R₂ = COCH₃
17d ; R₁ = C₆H₅-*n*, R₂ = COCH₂Cl
17e ; R₁ = CH₃, C₆H₅, R₂ = COCH₃
17f ; R₁ = CH₃, C₆H₅, R₂ = COCH₂Cl

Acylation of **15a** with acetyl chloride, chloroacetyl chloride and benzoyl chloride gave **16a-c**, respectively (ν_{NH} at 3 200, ν_{CO} at 1 710 and 1 690 cm^{-1} due to the amide and δ -lactone groups). Extension of this reaction to **15b-d** was also successful yielding **17a-f** as evident from elemental analyses and ir spectra (showing disappearance of ν_{NH}). Another supporting evidence for the structures of **16** and **17** was arrived at from alkylation of **16a** with benzyl chloride in acetone in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 to give **17e** (m.p. and m.m.p.). The sulphonyl chloride (**1**) was also

reacted with *p*-aminohippuric and with 5-aminosalicylic acid to give 18 and 19, respectively, as evident from analytical and ir spectral data and the fact that both 18 and 19 responded to the test for acidity.

The authors prepared another type of xanthotoxin derivatives derived from 4-aminoxanthotoxin¹¹ (20). Thus benzoic acid-3-sulphonyl chloride and salicylic acid-5-sulphonyl chloride were reacted with 20 to give 21a, b, respectively, in order to compare their biological activity with their isomers 3 and 19, respectively.

- 21
 21a; R₁=H, R₂=COOH
 21b; R₁=OH, R₂=COOH
 21c; R₁=NHCOOH⁻, R₂=H

Acetanilide-4-sulphonyl chloride was similarly reacted with 20 to give 21c. It was found that the latter group of compounds (21) gave better biological activity as indicated in Table 2.

Interaction of xanthotoxin with hydrazine hydrate gave the hydrazide (22a)¹² which reacted with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride to give 22b and with aldehydes to give the hydrazones (23a-e).

- 22
 22a; R=H
 22b; R=SO₂C₆H₄CH₃-*p*

- 23
 23a; R=C₆H₄OOCH₃-*p*
 23b; R=C₆H₄Cl-*o*
 23c; R=C₆H₄Cl-*p*
 23d; R=C₆H₄NO₂-*o*
 23e; R=C₆H₄NO₂-*p*

Some of the newly prepared xanthotoxin derivatives were tested against *Bacillus subtilis*, *B. cereus*, *B. mycoides*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salomonella typhosa* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. Results reported in Table 2 show that some of the derivatives display improved antimicrobial activities than the parent compound, with the highest activity being observed for compounds which contain either free aldehydic group (23c) or a halogen atom attached to aliphatic side chain (10c). Their antifungal activities are still under investigation.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				N	S
2a	87	213 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	6.20 (6.22)	14.30 (14.22)
2b	80	140 ^b	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	11.30 (11.38)	13.00 (13.01)
2c	85	253 ^a	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	10.70 (10.61)	12.10 (12.13)
2d	75	176 ^a	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	10.50 (10.33)	11.90 (11.81)
2e	75	170 ^a	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	10.10 (10.07)	11.70 (11.51)
3a	70	220 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₆ S	3.30 (3.37)	7.70 (7.71)
3b	60	238 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₆ S	3.30 (3.37)	7.60 (7.71)
3c	65	215 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₆ S	3.40 (3.37)	7.70 (7.71)
4a	50	135 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ NO ₆ S	3.00 (2.97)	6.70 (6.79)
4b	40	229 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ NO ₆ S	3.30 (3.26)	7.50 (7.46)
4c	55	205 ^b	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₆ S	3.10 (3.16)	7.30 (7.23)
4d	35	249 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ NO ₆ S	3.00 (2.97)	6.80 (6.79)
5a	55	225 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ S	6.00 (5.96)	6.90 (6.81)
5b	30	203 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ S	5.90 (5.96)	6.90 (6.81)
5c	40	185 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ S	5.70 (5.65)	6.50 (6.45)
5d	50	197 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ S	5.50 (5.56)	6.30 (6.35)
6a	34	149 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ S	5.90 (5.81)	6.70 (6.64)
6b	40	219 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ S	5.70 (5.79)	6.70 (6.61)
7a	70	258 ^c	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₇ S	3.60 (3.62)	8.30 (8.37)
7b	75	219 ^c	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₇ S	3.70 (3.62)	8.30 (8.27)
7c	80	241 ^c	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NO ₇ S	3.70 (3.62)	8.20 (8.27)
8a	50	175 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ NO ₇ S	3.00 (3.06)	7.00 (7.00)
8b	55	205 ^b	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ NO ₇ S	3.30 (3.26)	7.50 (7.46)
8c	35	221 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ NO ₇ S	3.10 (3.16)	7.30 (7.23)
8d	40	209 ^c	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ NO ₇ S	3.00 (2.97)	6.70 (6.79)
8e	30	225 ^{b,c}	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ NO ₇ S	3.00 (2.99)	6.90 (6.83)
9a	55	187 ^{b,c}	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ NO ₆ S	3.30 (3.26)	7.50 (7.46)
9b	60	171 ^c	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ NO ₆ S	3.20 (3.26)	7.50 (7.46)
9c	30	185 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ NO ₆ S	2.90 (2.85)	6.50 (6.53)
9d	35	251 ^c	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ NO ₆ SCI	2.70 (2.66)	6.10 (6.09)
10a	83	185 ^a	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₆ S	6.00 (6.06)	7.00 (6.93)
10b	65	219 ^c	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₇ S	5.50 (5.56)	6.30 (6.35)
10c	55	149 ^c	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₇ SCI	5.30 (5.20)	5.90 (5.94)
10d	35	235 ^c	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S	5.10 (5.13)	5.90 (5.86)
11	45	151 ^c	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₆ S	5.70 (5.76)	6.50 (6.58)
12	30	98 ^c	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	5.70 (5.69)	13.00 (13.01)

(Table 1 contd.)

13a	50	135 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₈ S	—	8.10 (8.00)
13b	50	225 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₈ S	—	8.00 (8.00)
13c	65	191 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₈ S	—	8.00 (8.00)
14	75	231 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₈ S	2.50 (2.58)	5.90 (5.89)
15a	65	281 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₉ NO ₈ S	4.70 (4.75)	10.90 (10.85)
15b	75	165 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₈ S	4.60 (4.53)	13.30 (10.36)
15c	80	175 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₈ S	4.00 (3.99)	9.00 (9.12)
15d	75	171 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₈ S	3.70 (3.64)	8.30 (8.31)
16a	70	209 ^b	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO ₇ S	4.00 (4.15)	9.50 (9.50)
16b	55	199 ^b	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO ₇ SCI	3.80 (3.77)	8.70 (8.61)
16c	35	239 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₇ S	3.50 (3.51)	8.00 (8.02)
17a	55	215 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₇ S	4.00 (3.99)	9.00 (9.12)
17b	45	199 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₇ SCI	3.70 (3.63)	8.30 (8.30)
17c	40	131 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₇ S	3.50 (3.56)	8.00 (8.14)
17d	35	139 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₇ SCI	3.30 (3.28)	7.50 (7.49)
17e	45	145 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₇ S	3.30 (3.28)	7.50 (7.49)
17f	30	63 ^d	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₇ SCI	3.00 (3.03)	7.00 (6.93)
18	70	285 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₈ S	6.00 (5.93)	6.70 (6.78)
19	75	150 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₈ S	3.30 (3.25)	7.50 (7.43)
21a	65	171 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₈ S	3.40 (3.37)	7.70 (7.71)
21b	55	185 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₈ S	3.30 (3.25)	7.50 (7.43)
21c	60	213 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₈ S	6.50 (6.54)	7.50 (7.43)
22b	75	211 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₈ S	7.00 (6.97)	7.90 (7.96)
23a	85	165 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₈	7.70 (7.65)	—
23b	80	209 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.60 (7.56)	—
23c	75	195 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.50 (7.56)	—
23d	80	203 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄	11.00 (11.02)	—
23e	70	281 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄	11.10 (11.02)	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Solvent for crystallisation: ^aacetone, ^bethanol, ^cbenzene, ^dpetroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye–Umicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer.

Xanthotoxin-4-sulphonamides (2a–e, 3a–c, 7a–c, 10a, 15b–d, 18 and 19): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol), the amino compound (0.01 mol) and pyridine (1 ml) in dry benzene (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 h. It was then concentrated, triturated with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was recrystallised from proper solvent to give the title compounds (Table 1).

Similarly, **21a–c** were prepared from 4-aminoxanthotoxin (**20**) and the corresponding sulphonyl chloride.

Esterification of 3a, c: A mixture of **3** (0.01 mol), the appropriate alcohol (30 ml) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (3 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h. It was then cooled and neutralised with Na₂CO₃ solution (10%) to give **4a–d** (Table 1).

Interaction of 3c with amines: A mixture of **3c** (0.01 mol) and the proper primary or secondary amine (0.01 mol) was suspended in dry toluene (30 ml), and PCl₅ (0.5 ml) was added to it. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 3 h, and toluene was then removed by steam distillation to give the primary (**5a–d**) or the secondary (**6a, b**) amides, respectively (Table 1).

Alkylation and acylation of 7b, c: To a solution of **7b, c** (0.01 mol) in dry acetone (30 ml), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.01 mol) and the corresponding alkyl halide or acid chloride (0.01 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h, and then filtered while hot and concentrated to give **8a–e** or **9a–d**, respectively (Table 1).

Interaction of 10a with acid chlorides or acetic anhydride: A mixture of **10a** (0.01 mol) and the corresponding acid chloride or acetic anhydride (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 h. Concentration of the reaction mixture gave **10b, c** or **10d**, respectively (Table 1).

The acridine derivative (11): A mixture of **10a** (0.01 mol), acetyl chloride (0.02 mol) and anhydrous ZnCl₂ (0.5 g) in dry benzene (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 h and then decomposed with ice-cold water (100 ml). The organic layer was then separated, dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated to give **11** (Table 1). Fusion of **10b** with anhydrous ZnCl₂ at 170° also gave **11**.

The phenothiazene derivative (12): A mixture of **10a** (0.01 mol), sulphur flower (0.02 mol) and iodine (0.1 g) in *o*-dichlorobenzene (5 ml) was heated at 200–10° for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and triturated with light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) to give **12** (Table 1).

The sulphonic acid esters (13a–c): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and the corresponding hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was heated with vigorous stirring at 60–70° till melting. Then 0.7 N NaOH solution (0.01 mol) was added to the fused mixture in portions over a period of 0.5 h. Heating and stirring were continued for further 0.5 h to give **13a–c** (Table 1).

Interaction of 13c with hippuric acid: A mixture of **13c** (0.01 mol), hippuric acid (0.01 mol) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.2 g) in Ac₂O (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 0.5 h and then cooled to yield **14** (Table 1).

Xanthotoxin-4-sulphonamide (15a): A solution of **1** (0.05 mol) in ammonium hydroxide (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h to give **15a** on cooling (Table 1).

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF SOME OF THE SYNTHESISED COMPOUNDS TOWARDS DIFFERENT MICROORGANISMS

Compd. no.	Minimum inhibitory concentration*					
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>B. mycoides</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhosa</i>	<i>P. chrysogenum</i>
Xanthotoxin	500	—	—	500	—	—
2c	125	125	125	—	—	—
2d	—	—	—	—	—	—
2e	125	125	125	—	—	—
4a	500	500	500	—	—	—
4b	—	—	—	—	—	—
10b	—	—	—	—	—	—
10c	62.5	125	125	—	—	—
13b	—	—	—	—	—	—
13c	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5
21a	—	—	—	—	—	—
21b	500	500	500	—	—	—
21c	125	125	125	500	500	—
23a	—	—	—	—	—	—
23b	500	500	500	—	—	—

* (—) = no activity.

Interaction of 15a-d with aliphatic acid chlorides: A mixture of 14a-d (0.01 mol), the acid chloride (0.01 mol) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h and then concentrated and poured onto ice-cold water to give 15a, b and 17a-f (Table 1). Alkylation of 16a with benzyl chloride in acetone in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 gave 17e (m.p., m.m.p.).

Interaction of 15a with benzoyl chloride: A mixture of 15a (0.01 mol) and benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) was heated at 180–90° for 1 h. It was then refluxed with ethanol containing charcoal for 0.5 h, filtered, concentrated and cooled to give 16c (Table 1).

Interaction of 22a with p-toluenesulphonyl chloride and aldehydes: A mixture of 22a (0.01 mol) and p-toluenesulphonyl chloride or the requisite aldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h to give 22b or 23a-d, respectively (Table 1).

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